

Theorems on the Binomial Coefficients for Combinatorial Geometric Series

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Abstract: This paper presents binomial and factorial theorems on the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series. The coefficient for each term in combinatorial geometric series refers to a binomial coefficient. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

MSC Classification codes: 05A10, 40A05 (65B10)

Keywords: computation, combinatorics, binomial coefficient

1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea was stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-13]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, binomial identities and multinomial theorem is provided using the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-13] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

Theorem 2.1: $pV_{qn}^{pn} = (p+q)V_{qn}^{pn-1}, (n, p, q \geq 1 \ \& \ n, p, q \in N)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Proof. } V_{qn}^{pn} &= \frac{(qn+1)(qn+2)(qn+3) \cdots (qn+pn-1)(qn+pn)}{(qn)!} \\ &= \frac{(qn+1)(qn+2)(qn+3) \cdots (qn+pn-1)(p+q)n}{(pn-1)! pn} \\ &= \frac{(p+q)n(qn+1)(qn+2)(qn+3) \cdots (qn+pn-1)}{(pn-1)! pn} \end{aligned}$$

$$= \left(\frac{p+q}{p}\right) \frac{(qn+1)(qn+2)(qn+3)\cdots(qn+pn-1)}{(qn-1)!} = \frac{(p+q)}{q} V_{qn}^{pn-1}.$$

$$\therefore V_{qn}^{pn} = \frac{(p+q)}{p} V_{qn}^{pn-1} \Rightarrow pV_{qn}^{pn} = (p+q)V_{qn}^{pn-1}, \quad (n, p, q \geq 1 \ \& \ n, p, q \in N).$$

Theorem 2.2: $qV_{pn}^{qn} = (p+q)V_{pn}^{qn-1}, \quad (n, p, q \geq 1 \ \& \ n, p, q \in N).$

Proof. $V_{pn}^{qn} = \frac{(pn+1)(pn+2)(pn+3)\cdots(pn+qn-1)(pn+qn)}{(qn)!}$

$$= \frac{(pn+1)(pn+2)(pn+3)\cdots(pn+qn-1)(p+q)n}{(qn-1)!qn}$$

$$= \frac{(p+q)n(pn+1)(pn+2)(pn+3)\cdots(pn+qn-1)}{(qn-1)!qn}$$

$$= \left(\frac{p+q}{q}\right) \frac{(pn+1)(pn+2)(pn+3)\cdots(pn+qn-1)}{(qn-1)!} = \frac{(p+q)}{q} V_{pn}^{qn-1}.$$

$$\therefore V_{pn}^{qn} = \frac{(p+q)}{q} V_{pn}^{qn-1} \Rightarrow qV_{pn}^{qn} = (p+q)V_{pn}^{qn-1}, \quad (n, p, q \geq 1 \ \& \ n, p, q \in N).$$

Corollary 2.1: $pV_{qn-k}^{pn-k} = (p+q)V_{qn-k}^{pn-k-1}, \quad (p \& q > k \geq 1, n \geq 1 \ \& \ k, n, p, q \in N).$

Corollary 2.2: $qV_{pn-k}^{qn-k} = (p+q)V_{pn-k}^{qn-k-1}, \quad (p \& q > k \geq 1, n \geq 1 \ \& \ k, n, p, q \in N).$

Corollary 2.3: $pV_{qn+k}^{pn+k} = (p+q)V_{qn+k}^{pn+k-1}, \quad (k, n, p, q \geq 1 \ \& \ n, p, q \in N).$

Corollary 2.4: $qV_{pn+k}^{qn+k} = (p+q)V_{pn+k}^{qn+k-1}, \quad (k, n, p, q \geq 1 \ \& \ n, p, q \in N).$

Conclusion

In this article, binomial and factorial theorems [1-13] were built using the binomial theorem on the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers for research and development further.

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